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CLINICAL, IMMUNOLOGICAL, RADIOLOGICAL AND PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF DESTRUCTIVE PROCESSES IN THE SPINE

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Osteoarticular tuberculosis, as the most frequent localization of extrapulmonary tuberculosis, remains one of the current medical and social problems. More than 80% of osteoarticular tuberculosis cases are spine tuberculosis. Before complications occur, symptoms are poor and non-specific.

Oncological patients' survival has improved due to the progress in cancer treatment, but the incidence of metastases has also increased. Metastases in 70-96% of cases localized in the spine.

Early differential diagnosis of inflammatory, metastatic lesions and cystic formations of the spine based on X-ray and tomographic data is difficult.

Thus, a systematic interdisciplinary diagnostic approach is needed for the early verification of spine tumorous and/or inflammatory diseases.

Keywords: spinal tuberculosis, vertebral metastases, differential diagnosis.

It is difficult to overestimate the severity of spinal disorders that physicians faced in the late nineteenth century: traumatic injuries, congenital defects, and tuberculosis or Pott's disease often resulted in severe neurologic impairment and global disability. Due to advances in antiseptic surgery and others and innovations in anesthesia, modern surgeons perform highly technologically advanced operations and help patients affected by spinal disorders [3,4].

Considering this issue, Prihodko S.A. (2016), notes that benign tumors of the musculoskeletal system are the most important direction in clinical oncology. The relevance of the problem under consideration is primarily due to a very young and, as a result, the most socially significant group of patients suffering from this pathology. More than 70% of patients with bone and soft tissue tumors are under 30 years old, 30% of them are children under 15 years old. At the same time, in the structure of oncological diseases, bone tumors constitute 1-4%. The diagnosis and selection of optimal treatment tactics for these new formations are possible only with a multidisciplinary approach [7,9].

New formations in the spine can arise from local sources, that is, be primary tumors of bone, fat, fibrous, nervous tissue, nerve sheaths, adjacent paravertebral soft tissues, and lymphatic vessels. However, they can also be secondary, or metastatic tumors, when cells from primary tumors spread to the spine hematogenously or through lymphatic pathways from distant malignant foci. Metastatic formations significantly prevail over primary ones, constituting up to 97% of all spinal neoplasms. Since the spine is well vascularized and has close connections with

regional lymphatic and venous drainage vessels, it is generally susceptible to metastasis. Studies show that almost 70% of patients with the most common malignant neoplasms—breast cancer, lung cancer, prostate cancer—have metastases in the bones, including the spine. Skeletal metastasis occurs in 70–80% of patients with breast or prostate cancer and in 40% of patients with advanced lung cancer [10, 11, 12].

Relying on this new classification system, scientists are reviewing the current knowledge of all tumor entities with spinal manifestations, their biological behavior and, most importantly, their relevant treatment options as well as the surgical approaches [9,13].

O.L. Kopchak and others (2016) presented the results of the study of clinical and laboratory features of nonbacterial osteomyelitis spinal lesions. Nonbacterial osteomyelitis (NBO) is a rare noninfectious autoinflammatory disease of the human skeleton, occurring mainly in children and adolescents, characterized by an unpredictable natural course associated with both repeated relapses and the possibility of spontaneous remission. The NBO pathogenesis is relatively well studied and is based on the imbalance between pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines - decreased production of interleukin-10 (IL-10) monocytes and increased inhibitor of tumor- α (TNF- α) necrosis factor.

5 patients were indicated for spinal surgery: in 4 cases, intervention was performed due to uninformative results of closed biopsy or pronounced spinal instability manifesting as a pain syndrome provoked by movements and uncontrollable with orthotics. In one case, reconstruction of the cervical spine was carried out due to spinal deformity development resulting from the affected C5 vertebra alongside ongoing treatment for nonbacterial osteomyelitis (NBO). In case of the necessity to combine conservative therapy and surgical treatment, the decision regarding the timing, tactics, and sequence of actions was discussed collegially. Surgeons determined the tactics and scope of the surgical treatment. A significant number of laboratory and instrumental studies are required for disease diagnostics, including an assessment of blood clinical analysis, acute-phase indicators, and mandatory radiographic visualization of the affected skeletal area. Changes detected in bone scintigraphy and MRI, primarily characterizing the metabolic activity of the process, may not be confirmed by X-rays and CT scans, which reflect the severity of destruction or reactive changes. The final diagnosis is made based on a combination of the morphological picture of the inflammatory process in the bone, while specific and nonspecific bacterial osteomyelitis, malignant and benign bone neoplasms are necessarily excluded. Therefore, bone biopsy with subsequent bacteriological and morphological examination is mandatory for the conclusive verification of the disease [17, 21, 22].

The primary leading clinical manifestations of inflammatory processes in the spine are three syndromes: 1) painful vertebrogenic; 2) systemic inflammatory reaction; 3) neurological disorders. Among them, the unresolved major issues are

considered to be severe neurological disorders, post-inflammatory orthopedic instability of the spine, and the systemic inflammatory reaction syndrome [34].

American authors Limaiem F, Byerly DW, Mabrouk A (2023) discuss the clinical manifestations of spinal osteoblastoma. Osteoblastoma usually occurs in the posterior elements of the spine and sacrum (approximately 30 to 40%). Other common sites include the lower jaw (referred to as cementoblastoma) and long tubular bones (lower > upper extremities), where it is typically observed in the metaphysis. A precise diagnosis of osteoblastoma is crucial for determining the appropriate treatment approach and prognosis. In most cases, clinical, radiological, and predominantly histopathological examinations form the basis for diagnosis. Osteoblastoma presents with variable radiological appearances, ranging from indolent to highly aggressive. Overall, osteoblastoma has a good prognosis, and patients often remain cancer-free after surgical treatment with intralesional curettage or marginal resection of the lesion. In cases not amenable to surgical excision, radiation therapy may be considered. In instances with more aggressive visualization and/or clinical features, it is necessary to differentiate between aggressive (epithelioid) osteoblastoma or osteoblastoma-like osteosarcoma, two borderline osteoblastic tumors. In rare cases, osteoblastoma may be associated with systemic symptoms such as fever, weight loss, and diffuse periostitis, referred to as toxic osteosarcoma [23].

A group of American scientists, Arvind V, Nevzati E, Ghaly M (2021), assessed primary extradural tumors of the spinal column. Out of 163 primary tumor formations in bones and soft tissues, 92 lesions were recorded along the axis of the spine. Among these 92 subjects, 54 had the potential for metastasis. The peak age ranged from congenital lesions to 72 years old. Recommended surgical treatment strategies were developed for each tumor formation, based on their capacity to locally destruct tissue, grow, recur after resection, undergo malignant transformation, and survival indicators. Additionally, potential systemic treatment recommendations were outlined for each tumor formation. Based on the 5th Edition of the WHO Classification of Bone and Soft Tissue Tumors, 92 out of 163 tumor formations were identified as potentially having spinal manifestations. Accurate preoperative tissue diagnosis and interdisciplinary case discussions are crucial. Surgical resection is indicated for a significant subgroup of patients and should be tailored to the specific biological behavior of the target tumor entity [83].

The group of researchers Mechri M, Riahi H, Sboui I (2018) notes that primary malignant tumors of the spine are rare and mainly include chordoma, chondrosarcoma, Ewing's sarcoma, or primitive neuroectodermal tumor (PNET), and osteosarcoma. Spinal tumors are quite uncommon in patients under 30 years old and are generally benign, except for Ewing's sarcoma and osteosarcoma. The evaluation of a patient with a spinal tumor typically involves radiography, computed tomography (CT), bone scintigraphy, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). CT surpasses conventional radiography in assessing the location of the lesion and analyzing tumor matrix and bone changes. Whole-body MRI is evaluated for various

oncological indications. MRI has unparalleled ability to assess bone marrow, soft tissues, and the spinal canal's extension, allowing the evaluation of the treatment response. Technetium bone scintigraphy can be useful for detecting bone involvement and documenting multifocality. Unfortunately, bone scintigraphy is nonspecific and often cannot distinguish between benign tumors, tumor-like conditions, and malignant tumors. The final diagnosis of spinal tumors is based not only on the patient's age and histological features but also on the tumor's topographical characteristics and the analysis of the imaging findings.

The study conducted by Chinese scientists Chen J, Shen Y, Shao X (2023) demonstrates the growing role of inflammation in spinal cord injury and spinal cord tumors. The role of inflammation in neuroinflammation related to various diseases is becoming increasingly important. The inflammasome is an intracellular multi-protein complex involved in activating caspase-1 and secreting pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin (IL)-1 β and IL-18. Inflammation in the spinal cord contributes to stimulating immune-inflammatory reactions by releasing pro-inflammatory cytokines, thereby mediating further damage to the spinal cord. In this review, they emphasize the role of the inflammasome in spinal cord injury and tumors. Targeting inflammation represents a promising therapeutic strategy for treating spinal cord injury and spinal cord tumors [89].

Gravallese EM (2017) highlights the significant impact of rheumatic diseases on bones, a phenomenon known since the early days of radiography. This influence varies significantly depending on the specific rheumatic condition. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is the most common form of inflammatory arthritis associated with bone destruction. Patients with RA suffer from erosion of joint bone and cartilage. Plain radiographs are widely used to detect and quantitatively assess bone erosion, evaluate structural joint damage, and monitor therapy effectiveness. Joint erosions closely correlate with disability in RA patients, and their significance is emphasized by their inclusion in the primary endpoints for managing this condition by the Food and Drug Administration.

In contrast, ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a rheumatic disease where inflammation contributes to bone formation, ultimately leading to spinal fusion and loss of spinal mobility. Conditions like psoriatic arthritis (PsA) represent a middle ground where joint erosions are observed in some joints while periarticular bone formation occurs in others, especially at tendon and ligament insertion sites into bone, known as entheses.

The work of American scientists in the laboratory has focused on determining the pathophysiological mechanisms through which inflammation in rheumatic diseases affects bones. The anatomical focus of inflammation plays a crucial role in the diverse impact of rheumatic diseases on bones. In RA, inflammation initially arises in the synovial membrane lining the diarthrodial joints, progressing to an intense immune-mediated process leading to the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines

and synovial tissue proliferation. This inflamed synovial tissue ultimately invades the bone marrow space deep within the joint surface, causing joint bone destruction.

In diseases associated with spondyloarthritis, such as AS, synovial membrane inflammation is also present in many cases. However, the initial site of inflammation in these diseases is the enthesis, including enthesal sites around the spine. The cell types, mediators, and pathways regulating bone tissue in these different anatomical sites differ, resulting in unique outcomes for bone.

The authors note that this work has led to the realization that many cytokines and factors known to regulate inflammation simultaneously play a critical role in bone homeostasis. This understanding has given rise to a new field called "osteimmunology," studying factors that influence both the immune system and bones [101].

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) serves as a prototype of inflammatory arthritis that leads to the loss of bone mass in joints (erosions), with osteoclasts being critical cells responsible for bone resorption in this condition. Cytokines crucial for bone resorption observed in RA include RANKL, necessary for this process and produced by cells in inflamed synovial tissues. Additionally, numerous pro-inflammatory cytokines locally produced in the joint contribute to bone erosion, either by inducing RANKL in local cell types or by acting synergistically with RANKL to promote the formation of osteoclasts, which resorb bone. Inflammation in RA also hinders bone formation by osteoblasts, exacerbating bone loss and impeding erosion recovery. Thus, even when patients are treated with disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs), halting the progression of erosions is possible, but erosion healing is rare, suggesting the persistence of residual subclinical inflammation in the joints. Conversely, patients with spondyloarthritis experience impaired bone formation in enthesal regions both in peripheral joints and the spine, leading to pain and reduced mobility. The mechanisms of bone formation in these diseases involve the activation of signaling pathways such as BMP and Wnt and cytokines including IL-17A, IL-22, and IL-23. These cytokines contribute to inflammation, osteoblast differentiation, and bone formation. Understanding these pathways has led to the development of new therapeutic strategies for treating patients with rheumatic diseases and protecting against disabling changes in bone homeostasis [103, 105, 107].

Mechri M, Riahi H, Sboui I (2018) state that spinal osteosarcoma comprises 3.6–14% of all primary spinal tumors and 4% of all osteosarcomas. They are more prevalent in older age groups than osteosarcoma in the appendicular skeleton (average age 38 years) and show a male predilection. In 79% of cases, the tumor arises in the posterior elements with partial involvement of the vertebral body. Involvement of two spinal levels is observed in 17% of cases. Radiographs and Computer Tomography scans typically display a mixed osteosclerotic-osteolytic lesion. A heterogeneous mass of soft tissue with ossified and non-ossified components is usually associated. Rarely, tumors with significant mineralization arising in the vertebral body may present as an "ivory vertebra" (sclerosing

osteoblastic osteosarcoma). A purely lytic appearance is also observed in various subtypes, such as telangiectatic osteosarcoma (predominant cystic architecture, mimicking an aneurysmal bone cyst). The mineralized component of the tumor shows low signal intensity on both T1-weighted images (WI) and T2-WI, whereas the non-mineralized component displays high signal intensity on T2-WI. Fluid-fluid levels have been described in association with telangiectatic osteosarcoma. Expansive cortical destruction, soft tissue extension, and pathological fractures may be observed. Local recurrence rates are estimated at 20% following en bloc resection and 60% following intralesional resection [110].

Chondrosarcoma constitute a heterogeneous group of tumors characterized by their ability to form cartilage. Chondrosarcoma accounts for 10% of all primary bone tumors and less than 12% may arise in the spine. The thoracic spine is the most frequent localization (accounting for 60%), followed by the cervical and lumbar spine. Spinal chordosarcoma can arise in the posterior elements (40%), in the vertebral body, or in both. Males are affected two to four times more than females, and the average age of patients is 45 years. Most lesions represent primary chondrosarcoma; however, secondary chondrosarcoma may also occur when an osteochondroma (solitary or multiple with hereditary multiple exostoses) undergoes malignant transformation. Radiographs demonstrate a well-defined mass with internal calcinates. Mineralization of the chondroid matrix is better demonstrated by Computer Tomography, showing typical "rings and arcs". Computed Tomography can demonstrate geographic osteolysis with sclerotic margins.

Baroncini A, Berjano P, Migliorini F (2022) Spinal Destructive Osteoarthritis (SDOA) is characterized by rapidly developing edema of the vertebral endplates, followed by the destruction of the disc space within a few months from the initial diagnosis. The disease progresses in the involved segment and neighboring discs despite surgical therapy. Surgical planning should take into account the disruption of the bone structure, and the use of large interbody cages or 4-rod constructs should be considered to achieve a stable construct. As an example, a case of spinal osteoarthritis is considered, which, also due to diagnostic delays, underwent multiple revisions for implant failure with subsequent coronal and sagittal imbalance. In a 37-year-old otherwise healthy woman, non-traumatic lower back pain appeared. After initial conservative treatment, subsequent imaging revealed rapidly progressing erosion of the vertebral endplate and scoliotic deformation. Following surgical treatment, the patient underwent numerous revisions for pseudoarthrosis, coronal and sagittal imbalance, and connective tissue insufficiency, despite initially observing proper alignment after each operation. Since mechanical overload from insufficient spine alignment correction was ruled out, the authors believe that multiple complications were caused by a disruption in bone structure. Thus, reviewing old imaging, they diagnosed the patient with spinal SDOA. In the case of spinal SDOA, special attention should be paid to the selection of the degree and type of instrumentation to prevent further interventions [87].

Mireles-Cano JN, Gonzalez AM (2021) Scientists from the Brazilian Society of Orthopedics and Traumatology conducted a study on patients with vertebral destruction syndrome. Percutaneous transpedicular vertebral biopsies were performed under fluoroscopic guidance, extracting bone tissue and intervertebral disc tissue; histopathological and microbiological studies were also conducted. They analyzed age, gender, spinal segment, neurological status, as well as biopsy and culture results. The results showed that the average age of patients was 53.8 years (range: 2 to 83 years), with the lumbar segment being the primary segment in 62% of cases. According to the American Spinal Injury Association (ASIA) impairment scale, before surgery, 49% of patients were classified as ASIA E, and all of them experienced pain. The final etiology was identified in 83% of the sample. Etiology was grouped into three categories: infectious, neoplastic, and degenerative (osteoporotic). The infectious group comprised 36% of patients, with *Staphylococcus aureus* being the most commonly identified agent in 34.9% of cases. The etiology was neoplastic in 34.9%, with multiple myeloma and metastatic disease from prostate cancer being the most common. Osteoporosis was present in 21.7% of patients. The average surgery time was 47.5 minutes, with an average blood loss of 10 ml. No complications were reported. Percutaneous biopsy under fluoroscopic guidance had an 83% effectiveness for etiological diagnosis of vertebral destruction syndrome in this series. It should be considered a useful minimally invasive procedure that is simple, economical, reproducible, and associated with a low risk of short-term and long-term complications [103].

Percutaneous vertebral biopsy is less invasive, cost-effective, and suitable for patients experiencing persistent back pain and vertebral body lesions detected through non-invasive imaging methods.

Ravikanth R (2020) Fluoroscopy-guided transcutaneous transpedicular spinal biopsies were performed on 42 patients with spinal pathology through a posterior transpedicular approach. Out of the 42 patients, 28 were male (66.7%), and 14 were female (33.3%). Spinal involvement was observed more in the lower thoracic region (26.2%), followed by the upper dorsal region (7.1%), L1 (23.6%), L2 (6.4%), L3 (14.6%), L5 (17.3%), and the sacrum (4.8%). Twenty-one cases with neoplastic etiology were identified (14 metastases, 2 malignant round cell tumors, 2 multiple myelomas, and 3 lymphomas), 14 cases of tuberculosis (TB), 4 osteomyelitis, 2 inflammatory, and 1 isolated compression fracture. Twelve patients out of the 14 diagnosed with tuberculosis by histopathology had positive tuberculosis cultures and sensitivity patterns. Fluoroscopy-guided transcutaneous transpedicular biopsy with a 3.1 mm internal diameter Jamshidi trocar is a simple, safe, and reliable method for etiological diagnosis of vertebral lesions. However, the success of this method depends on the precise placement of the trocar and close interdisciplinary clinical collaboration. This minimally invasive technique is straightforward, safe, and effective in diagnosing malignant and infectious spinal lesions [111].

Khankan A, Sirhan S, Aris F. (2015) Percutaneous needle biopsy of spinal lesions can be performed on an outpatient basis with a low level of complications such as bleeding, infection, and contamination of the biopsy tract. Additionally, if indicated, it allows for subsequent radiotherapy, avoiding issues related to wounds. The procedure can be done under local anesthesia and conscious sedation. This provides monitoring of nerve root function during the procedure and helps minimize discomfort. Percutaneous biopsy can be performed under fluoroscopic guidance or can be done as a CT-guided biopsy. Although CT-guided biopsy seemingly offers precise identification of the lesion, there are several drawbacks such as cost, radiation exposure, continuous monitoring is not possible, and real-time needle positioning is also not possible. Fluoroscopy technique offers several advantages, as it can be done in a well-equipped facility in aseptic conditions, and in case of a severe complication, surgical intervention can be undertaken immediately. Real-time needle positioning is possible, and the amount of radiation is also low compared to CT-guided biopsy. Transpedicular lesions of the vertebrae located just in front of the pedicle and the disc space are accessible. Complications of this method arise when there is a violation of the medial or lower wall of the pedicle, leading to spinal cord injury or nerve root damage. Moreover, if the biopsy needle penetrates too deeply, it may puncture the aorta or the inferior vena cava [89].

The study conducted by Krivoshein A.E. et al. in 2020 examines the morphological and radiographic parameters of the facet joints depending on the degree of intervertebral disc degeneration. For the lumbar spine facet joints of 145 patients with different stages of degeneration according to Pfirrmann, who underwent surgery using rigid fixation and TLIF technology, dual-energy CT scans and morphological examination of the operative material were conducted.

In cases with Pfirrmann II, an increase in the volumetric content of chondrocytes, density of the cartilaginous plate according to Hounsfield units, and calcium levels in the facet joints were visualized, indicating the preservation of joint functionality. In Pfirrmann V cases, profound pathological changes occurred with disruption of the architecture of the facet joint cartilaginous structures, formation of bone elements, and ingrowth of connective tissue into cartilaginous and bone structures of the joint, correlating with the CT scan results.

In the morphological analysis of the operative material in the Pfirrmann II group, initial signs of pathological bone regeneration were noted in the form of singular bone trabeculae ingrowth from the subchondral layers of the facet joint towards the cartilaginous plate. In 28 observations within this group, active regeneration of chondrocytes in the deep layers of the cartilaginous plate was observed near the bone trabeculae. A statistically significant increase in the volumetric content of chondrocytes in the superficial zone of the cartilage was found, attributed to the increase in three- and four-cell lacunae while concurrently decreasing the number of single-cell lacunae, indicating the activation of reparative processes.

The study demonstrates a close correlation between morphological and radiological changes in facet joints. The comparison of these findings allows for objective criteria to assess the degree of pathological processes in facet joints, serving as a diagnostic component in planning decompression-stabilizing procedures for patients with degenerative lumbar spine diseases. The research underscores the essential link between morphological and radiological changes in facet joints and their utility in planning decompression-stabilizing procedures for patients with degenerative lumbar spine diseases, guiding the choice of spine fixation techniques [44, 45].

The study by Konev V.P. and colleagues (2020) reviews morphologic changes in a facet joint at different stages of intervertebral disc degeneration. They studied the facet joints of the lumbar spine in 145 patients with different degrees of degeneration according to the Pfirrmann scale who underwent surgery using rigid fixation and TLIF technology, and performed morphologic analysis of the surgical material. The results showed that as the degree of disc degeneration increased, the volume content of chondrocytes decreased significantly, and there was a reorganization of the joint microarchitecture due to the infiltration of bone trabeculae and connective tissue into their structure. These changes resulted in impaired articular cartilage thickness, sclerosis, and disruption of the connections between cartilage and bone elements, ultimately leading to functional loss of the joint. The authors revealed that at the Pfirrmann II stage, there was preservation of the volume content of chondrocytes, indicating preservation of joint functionality and allowing the use of dynamic fixation as a surgical strategy. However, in severe disc degeneration (Pfirrmann V stage), deep pathologic changes occurred in the facet joints, including disruption of the architectonics of all joint elements: formation of deficient cartilage zones, formation of bone structures, and penetration of connective tissue into cartilage and bone structures. The preferred technique in such cases is the use of a rigid fixation of the affected spinal segment to restore its stability.

Karajaeva S.A., Torchynov I.A. evaluated the levels of TNF-alpha, IL-1, and IL-2 cytokines in patients with lower back pain related to short and long articular processes of the lumbar vertebrae. Among 418 patients with lower back pain examined by X-ray, excessively long, excessively short, and average sizes of the articular processes of the lumbar vertebrae were identified. Using immunoassay methods, patients with lower back pain with excessively long and excessively short articular processes of the lumbar vertebrae showed higher serum levels of TNF-alpha and IL-1 and lower levels of IL-2 compared to those with average-sized articular processes. These findings indicate a pronounced immune response capable of sustaining inflammation and disease progression. It has been demonstrated that serum levels of TNF-alpha and IL-1, as well as the elevation of IL-2 levels due to therapy, serve as indicators of treatment effectiveness [35].

Zakhmatova T.V. and others (2012) evaluated the capabilities and informativeness (sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy) of the duplex (triplex) scanning method in the diagnosis of vertebral artery pathology in patients

with degenerative dystrophic diseases of the cervical spine. An evaluation of blood flow in the vertebral arteries of 180 patients with various clinical manifestations of degenerative-dystrophic diseases in the cervical spine was conducted using duplex scanning with the General Electric "VividS6" apparatus. Spectral and quantitative indicators of blood flow were determined, including peak systolic blood flow velocity (Vps), end diastolic blood flow velocity (Ved), time-averaged maximum blood flow velocity (TAMX), Gosling's pulsatility index (PI), and Pursel's resistance index (RI) in four segments of the vertebral artery (V1-V4) and the main artery (MA), as well as volumetric blood flow velocity (Vvol) in V1-V3 segments of the vertebral artery.

The color duplex scanning method enables the detection of deformities in the course of the vertebral artery within the bony canal (in 73% of cases): angular deformations, C, S, V-shaped twists (primarily at the level of C4-C5-C6 vertebrae) and assesses the gradient of velocity parameters in the area of these twists. Hemodynamically insignificant acceleration of TAMX (up to 30%) in the area of vertebral artery deformities from the initial blood flow velocity upon entering the bony canal was observed in 55% of cases, while in the remaining patients (45%), it was hemodynamically significant (more than 30%).

The method allows for the determination not only of local hemodynamic shifts but also of linear and volumetric blood flow velocities in the V3 segment of the vertebral artery, the ratio of Vvol in the V3 segment to the V1 segment, quantitatively calculating the degree of blood flow compensation. In most cases (78%), there was no decrease in linear (TAMX) and volumetric blood flow velocities in the V3 segment compared to the V1 segment (compensated blood flow).

Decompensated (with a ratio of Vvol in the V3 segment to the V1 segment less than 0.7) and subcompensated (with a ratio of Vvol in the V3 segment to the V1 segment between 0.7 and 0.9) blood flow was associated not only with local vertebrogenic influences on the vertebral artery and disturbance of vascular geometry but also with diffuse atherosclerotic artery lesions, hypertensive, diabetic angiopathy, and congenital anomalies of diameter and entry level of the vertebral artery into the bony canal. Using duplex scanning, it is possible to establish the presence of systemic blood flow deficiency in the vertebrobasilar basin: a decrease in linear blood flow velocity in the intracranial (V4) segment of the vertebral artery and MA (in 8% of cases). Quantitatively determining the degree of severity of vertebrobasilar insufficiency allows for the calculation of the total volumetric blood flow in the vertebral arteries, which normally ranges from 180 to 200 ml/min. In patients with degenerative-dystrophic diseases of the cervical spine (excluding cases of atherosclerotic lesions and congenital anomalies of the vertebral artery), the indicator was 181 ± 43 ml/min. The method enables a reliable assessment of hemodynamics in the vertebral arteries, velocity gradients, volumetric blood flow throughout the extracranial segments of the vertebral artery, and the systemic hemodynamic significance of extravascular influences [30].

The accurate diagnosis of changes in the spine (assessing localization, extent, and activity level) will enable timely implementation of the correct treatment approach and, consequently, prevent the development of irreversible complications in the future.

Nowadays, computed tomography is widely used among radial methods of diagnosing degenerative-dystrophic changes of the spine. Computed tomography is based on the radiologic method that allows obtaining cross-sectional layer-by-layer images of the spine, differentiating intraspinal structures and detecting differences in the density of normal and pathologically altered tissues.

The authors Ni J, Zheng Y, Liu N (2015) consider the radiological assessment of anterior lumbar interbody fusion (ALIF) with the use of PEEK cells along with adjacent autologous spine grafts during prolonged spinal deformity surgeries. ALIF is a well-established method for treating structural instability associated with symptomatic disc degeneration. The aim of lumbar fusion is to create an environment that allows bones to form a solid bony bridge through the involved spinal segments. Autologous iliac crest bone (AICB) stands as the gold standard due to its ideal characteristics as a transplant, including osteoconduction, osteoinduction, and osteogenesis. Despite numerous advantages, ALIF with a bone graft as an independent procedure is associated with high rates of non-fusion (44%), subsidence, and graft extrusion. These complications stem from inadequate stability for interbody fusion.

The combined anterior and posterior approach is often a preferred option, especially for correcting spinal deformities in adults with severe low lumbar curvature. Femoral ring allografts (FRAs), packed with autograft bone and used in combination with posterior instruments, have shown promising fusion rates and restoration of sagittal alignment in spinal deformities. This approach also helps avoid morbidity at donor sites. However, bones are less stable at the endplate interface and often require additional anterior or posterior fixation.

Locally collected vertebral body bone was used in this study to fill the interbody spaces, avoiding both the cost of bone graft substitutes and the morbidity associated with harvesting bone from the iliac crest. The goals of this research involved radiographic evaluation of the utility of PEEK cells, packed with local vertebral autografts, in the anterior lumbar intervertebral space during prolonged lumbar-sacral spinal fusions. The authors assume that locally collected lumbar body bone will have a better fusion rate. Moreover, it has been proven that removing a sufficient amount of bone from the anterior aspect of the adjacent lumbar spine does not significantly weaken the vertebral body [113].

The multi-layer ("multispiral", "multislice") computed tomography was first introduced in 1992. The principal difference between multispiral CT scanners and those of previous generations is that not one, but two or more rows of detectors are arranged around the circumference of the gantry. In order that X-ray radiation could be simultaneously received by detectors, located on different rows, a new

(volumetric) geometric shape of the beam was developed. In 1992, the first two-slice (two-spiral) MSCT with two rows of detectors appeared, and in 1998, four-slice (four-spiral), with four rows of detectors, respectively. In addition to the above features, the number of X-ray tube revolutions was increased from one to two per second. In 2004-2005, 32-, 64- and 128-slice CT scanners were introduced, including those with two X-ray tubes. Today, some treatment facilities already have 320-slice CT scanners. These CT scanners, first introduced in 2007, are a new round in the evolution of X-ray computed tomography. They allow not only to obtain images, but also make it possible to observe almost "in real" time physiological processes occurring in the brain and heart. The peculiarity of such a system is the possibility of scanning an entire organ (heart, joints, brain, etc.) in one revolution of the beam tube, which significantly reduces the examination time [104].

Tsybulskaya Y.A.(2015) Radiological methods of examination play a leading role in the diagnosis of bone destructive changes in tuberculous lesions of the spine. The radiation picture of tuberculous spondylitis depends on the duration of the process. Each method of radiation diagnostics has its advantages and disadvantages in examining patients at different phases of the disease (pre-spondylitic, spondylitic, and osteospondylitic). With traditional radiography, tuberculous changes in the spine can be detected only a few months after the development of the infectious process. Early changes in the spine, when bone beams are slightly destroyed by granulation tissue, are not sufficiently characterized on the images and may remain undetected, which is a disadvantage of this method. Isolated tuberculous osteitis also causes diagnostic difficulties on radiographs in up to 20% of cases, especially when localized in the spinous processes and vertebral arches. In such cases, CT scanning is preferable. CT significantly improves the diagnosis of tuberculous spondylitis and makes it possible to assess the depth of contact destruction of vertebrae, the state of the spinal canal, the spread of the process to neighboring vertebrae (contact destruction), and to detect bone destruction at early stages (including in areas difficult for radiological examination - suboccipital, cervical-thoracic, lumbosacral).

The use of computed tomography, however, is limited in severe spinal deformities and also in large tuberculous lesions of the spine, which requires knowledge of a clear topical location based on neurologic status or prior spinal radiography or MRI [68].

Scientific and technological progress has made a significant expansion of radiotherapy possibilities, as an example: the conformal methods of irradiation are being implemented with the possibility of concentrating the radiation dose in a limited zone, allowing to overcome the problems of radioresistance of some neoplasms. The combination of radiosurgery and minimally invasive decompression of the spinal canal has led to the creation of a new direction in the treatment of metastatic epidural compression - separation surgery.

The diagnosis of the spinal column includes both non-invasive and invasive methods. Non-invasive methods include radiographic studies such as X-rays,

computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), as well as a radiological method called scintigraphy. It is proposed to perform a biopsy of the vertebral body. Invasive methods include four types of biopsies: fine-needle aspiration, trephine biopsy (using a thick needle to obtain a core tissue sample), open incisional biopsy (sampling a fragment of the vertebral body), and excisional biopsy (total removal of the vertebral body with biopsy). Open incisional biopsy is the standard in all cases where there is uncertainty about the histological nature of the tumor.

The modern classifications of hematogenous osteomyelitis of the spine are applicable in clinical practice and allow standardizing treatment regimens. The tactics are determined not only by the degree of destruction, involvement of paravertebral tissues, biomechanical instability of the affected spine and the presence of neurologic deficit, but also by the presence of systemic inflammatory response syndrome. In this regard, it is reasonable to introduce additional subtypes into the classifications that characterize the septic course of the disease and determine the indications for sanitizing and reconstructive ventral interventions. When the patient's condition is stabilized, these interventions can be supplemented with instrumental fixation of the spine.

The positive assessment of minimally invasive technology in spinal metastasis surgery has been noted by several scientists (Conti A., Acker G., 2019; Dalbayrak S., Yaman O., Ozer A.F., 2015). The trauma associated with traditional approaches to thoracic and lumbar vertebrae can be reduced by employing thoracoscopic surgery, endoscopic assistance, and minimally invasive open approaches. The incorporation of Minimally Invasive Spine Surgery (MISS) experience into the practice of treating metastases in the spine involves the use of percutaneous stabilization techniques, mini-approaches utilizing tubular retractors [118, 121].

Pennington Z. S. and co-authors (2018), having analyzed the results of treatment of patients with metastases to the spine, operated using standard and MISS-methods, concluded that minimally invasive surgery serves as a method of choice for that category of patients who, due to severity, are not subject to open intervention with long duration and intraoperative blood loss [115].

The third important trend is palliative minimally invasive surgical interventions for pain syndrome due to metastatic vertebral lesions - vertebroplasty, kyphoplasty and radiofrequency ablation. Percutaneous vertebroplasty is considered an effective intervention for osteolytic metastases to vertebral bodies, especially in multiple lesions and pathological vertebral fractures, including as part of combined treatment. Radiofrequency ablation of metastases to the spine was proposed by M. P. Goetz and co-authors(2004). This method is most effective in combination with vertebroplasty and should not be used as an isolated method of treatment.

Song H. M. and co-authors (2014) proposed a new method to perform palliative XL of metastases to the spine - interventional removal of the tumor. Injection of several milliliters of bone cement (vertebroplasty) is performed in the

zone of intervention at the end of surgery. The authors of the method evaluated its effectiveness and safety compared to conventional vertebroplasty in a prospective study of 124 patients, revealing a significant regression of pain syndrome in the postoperative period and an increase in patient mobility [96].

Bazarov A.Y. (2020) reports an analysis of the efficiency of conservative treatment and extra-axial transpedicular fixation in patients with uncomplicated course of «hematogenous osteomyelitis of the spine». The number of men amounted to 73.2 % (n = 71), women 26.8 % (n = 26). Acute and subacute forms of the disease were diagnosed in 62 (63.9 %) patients, chronic in 35 (36.1 %). According to Pola classification 45 patients were classified as type A, B 49, C 3. Conservative treatment was used in 64 (66.0%) patients, transpedicular fixation was applied in 33 (34.0%) and minimally invasive fixation in 25 (75.8%). Fixators were not placed in the affected vertebrae. All patients were treated with antibacterial therapy for 6-12 weeks. Good treatment results were obtained in 89 (91.8%) patients. There were no differences in the severity of pain syndrome between the comparison groups before treatment and after 1 year; however, in the dynamics before and after treatment, the severity of pain syndrome significantly decreased ($p=0.001$). When transpedicular fixation was used, positive results were obtained in 28 (84.8 %) cases, and after three repeated interventions in 32 (94.1 %), with conservative treatment in 61 (95.3 %). The total number of recurrences was 8 (8.2 %), complications 3 (3.1 %). The risk of relapse among operated drug addicts was significantly higher ($p = 0.033$). There were no fatal outcomes in the comparison groups, which is explained by the inclusion and exclusion criteria. All treated patients were followed up after discharge on an outpatient basis for at least 1 year, 72.2% from 1 to 8 years. Transpedicular fixation is indicated in uncomplicated course of hematogenous osteomyelitis of the spine, monosegmental lesions and high quality of life requirements. The use of this therapy in people addicted to drugs is not recommended [9].

The minimally invasive treatment of paravertebral abscesses resulting from nonspecific spondylodiscitis (clinical observations) by a group of scientists from Volgograd [57]. Nonspecific purulent-inflammatory spinal lesions are rare and difficult-to-diagnose conditions. The relevance of the problems in diagnosis and treatment is due to the increasing frequency of their occurrence, delayed detection (the period from the onset of the first symptoms to confirmation of the diagnosis can range from 2 weeks to 9 months, averaging 2-4 months), a high rate of diagnostic errors (up to 30-85% of cases), a high percentage of disability (up to 85%), emergence of new antibiotic-resistant strains of microorganisms, severity of the disease course, potential for infection generalization, lack of a unified surgical approach and unsatisfactory treatment outcomes.

Any part of the spine and adjacent tissues can potentially be involved in the purulent-inflammatory process. Nonspecific purulent-inflammatory spinal diseases (NPISD) constitute a group of inflammatory-destructive diseases of the spine and its structural elements (vertebral bodies, intervertebral discs, musculoskeletal apparatus,

intervertebral joints), caused by nonspecific pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microflora. The lumbar spine is most commonly affected - in 50-55% of cases, thoracic - in 20-35%, and the sacral and cervical regions account for up to 10-25%. There is also possible contamination of the para-vertebral soft tissues and the formation of paravertebral abscesses.

In cases of prolonged back pain, that is not relieved by nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, increased erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and C-reactive protein (CRP), presence of risk factors (diabetes mellitus, established intravenous catheter, intravenous drug addiction, immunosuppression, oncological processes, pyelonephritis, liver cirrhosis, alcoholism, rheumatoid arthritis, spinal trauma, spinal surgery, undrained lesions), MRI/CT of the spine is indicated to exclude this pathology. Conservative therapy may be considered independently only with minimal neurological symptoms and absence of pathological bone fractures penetrating the spinal canal. Surgical treatment is indicated for worsening neurological deficits, progression of spinal deformity or instability, spinal canal compression with spinal cord compression, severe and persistent pain not responding to conservative therapy, and the presence of formed abscesses with sepsis.

Sanitation and drainage of the purulent focus can be performed as a standalone operation or may be the first stage of treatment before radical-reconstructive and reconstructive surgeries.

The results of operations involving interbody titanium implants in over 1500 patients have been studied. Revision surgeries with implant removal were performed in 11 patients. Through the analysis of this group, three variations of local changes were identified: normal bone fusion of varying degrees (6 cases), disrupted osteoreparation and lack of bone fusion (3 cases), and late chronic infectious processes in the operated segment (2 cases). Morphological examination of tissue within the implants revealed spongy bone, cartilage, signs of chondral osteogenesis amidst chronic aseptic productive inflammation, and deposits of black particles (products of titanium alloy wear) in the formed connective tissue.

Analysis of the material revealed three circumstances necessitating revision interventions with implant removal. While insufficient decompression is an evident reason related to the surgical intervention itself, infection and aseptic instability require separate discussion. Surgical infection following spinal surgery is a serious complication with severe consequences. Infectious complications can be deeply localized despite the wound having already healed. The primary causative agent remains *Staphylococcus aureus*. Certain preoperative risk factors increase the frequency of local infection, mainly diabetes, smoking, steroid hormone intake, and perioperative factors such as blood transfusion. Furthermore, intraoperative risk factors include the invasiveness of the operation and the type of spinal fusion. The use of internal fixation increases the risk of infection by 28%. Implants provide an avascular surface for the formation of bacterial biofilm and serve as a focus for microbial growth. This diminishes the effectiveness of antimicrobial therapy and the

patient's immune system activity. In cases of late infectious complications, removal or replacement of implants is recommended.

A. V. Morev and colleagues (2019) propose a new method for diagnosing lumbar spondyloarthritis using an original assessment scale. The study presents the results of applying an original assessment scale for diagnosing lumbar spondyloarthritis (LSA). The scale is based on the determination of the following indicators: disease onset, patient's age, pain localization, presence or absence of neurological symptoms, assessment of movements in the lumbar spine, radiological changes in the facet joints, and dynamics of pain after injecting a mixture of anesthetic and corticosteroid into the facet joint area. This developed evaluation scale was used in diagnosing degenerative-dystrophic disease of the lumbar spine and determining treatment tactics in 67 patients. In all cases, it was possible to verify the cause of pain syndrome and achieve clinical efficacy of therapy using minimally invasive and interventional techniques. Considering the simplicity and efficiency of the new method for diagnostics of lumbar spondyloarthritis, it is reasonable to use it in practical healthcare, which will allow to determine the optimal treatment tactics for patients in a timely manner. The scaling up of interventional methods of therapy of degenerative and dystrophic spine diseases, especially in spondyloarthritis, contributes to the improvement of patients' quality of life, reduction of temporary disability, and reduction of the number of side effects arising from prolonged conservative treatment with various medications.

Z.P. Makhmudova (2022) introduces the possibilities of assessing the informativeness of diagnostic puncture trepanation biopsies for differential diagnosis of destructive spinal lesions in patients of different age groups. Closed percutaneous trepan biopsies of vertebrae are an informative, relatively safe method of interventional diagnostics of spinal lesions, which should be used for preoperative differentiation of inflammatory (tuberculous and nonspecific spondylitis), traumatic and tumor diseases accompanied by destruction of one vertebral-motor segment. The diagnostic informativeness of the method in limited destructive processes is relatively high, reaching 75.0% in adults. Within the structure of mono-segmental spinal destructions with suspicion of tuberculous spondylitis, nonspecific spondylitis prevails in adults, along with tumorous lesions, including malignant ones. The most severe complications of percutaneous trepanobiopsies of the vertebrae were not due to technical reasons but were caused by the progression of nonspecific inflammatory processes (epiduritis) against the background of spinal osteomyelitis. Transient complications such as radiculopathy and pneumothorax, when timely recognized and adequately treated, did not result in clinical consequences. The authors suggest that the informativeness of cytological and histological studies of the material obtained during trepanobiopsy may be higher if this manipulation is performed as early as possible, before initiating antibacterial or antitubercular therapy for the patient, combined with aspiration biopsy of material with additional bacteriological and cytological studies in the presence of a para-vertebral soft tissue component [48].

We can conclude the literature review by saying that the analysis of the domestic and foreign literature considering the issues of differential diagnosis of destructive processes in the spine is currently a difficult complex problem that requires consideration of neurosurgical, surgical, orthopedic, and immunologic aspects for successful implementation. The existing treatment is still characterized by a high frequency of cause-and-effect unsatisfactory outcomes. This is caused by continuing problems with early diagnosis and hospitalization of patients in specialized institutions, the lack of unified algorithms for diagnosis, tactics and routing of patients, standardization of indications and methods of surgical treatment of NSAIDs, insufficient consideration of systemic inflammatory factors in planning surgical treatment, the emergence of "new" groups of patients with comorbid features, including HIV (+), requiring a separate tactical approach and algorithm for the choice of surgical tactics, techniques and prophylaxis in the following areas.

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